

The Problems of Third World and United Nations

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ABSTRACT: In the International scenario, the world order is shifting from time to time. From post-modernism to the current modern era, the terms and relations of the countries have been gone through changes. The previous First, Second and Third world concepts are still going through alteration. The term "third world" was coined to designate nations that did not develop economically capitalist (the first world) nor was part of the communist system of the Soviet Union (second world). The term became inappropriate and then later disappeared. But the recent history of each country has forced us to rethink about the nations who are considered within or outside the group. Based on the characteristics which each class possesses out of the all the existing countries of the world. The main international organization United Nations must revisit the reforms and ought to bound the member states to follow international law. As the exploitations and balance of the power should be maintained. The key role is of the United Nations to maintain the development in all countries of the world.

KEYWORDS: Term, Third World, United Nations, Role, Development

Introduction

The first French economist to use this distinction is said as Alfred Sowie, in a 1952 issue of the magazine L'Observateur, entitled "Three Worlds, One Planet". It was in the Third World countries of Asia, Africa and Latin America, marking the third state in the French Revolution. It was then agreed that the economic and political situation was similar to that of countries in the south of the planet, so the term could refer to both geographical location and the level of geopolitics or economic development (Worsley 1970).

For this reason, it is difficult to find a country as a Third World because everyone's circumstances have changed, making it difficult to put them all in the same category. However, efforts are still being made to list and limit their features.

Features

The importance of the term is its ultimate goal that the countries in this category have all kinds of support from the rest of the world. The current international policy seeks to develop strategies to reduce inequality by focusing on third world countries. Below we describe the most prominent features of the countries belonging to this country:

Small Technical Development

In Third World countries, some of the available technological advances are usually introduced by foreign companies or other countries with economic activities. Only those involved in these activities have access to technology, while most of the population is completely unaware of it. It refers not only to communication technology but also to other areas of life such as transport, infrastructure, health, basic services and education, which directly affect the quality of life of its inhabitants (Cooke 2004).

Low Level of Industrialization

As a result of very little technological advancement and low level of education, it can be said that the so-called Industrial Revolution did not pass close to these countries. Their production

systems are neither dangerous nor very efficient, both in terms of technology and process. This often leads to wastage, misuse or low productivity of the natural resources available to these countries (Cooke 2004).

Economy dependent on exports of agricultural products and raw materials

Since its production process is quite obsolete and the small technology in it is usually carried out by foreign agents (foreign companies and other countries), its economy is mainly based on basic products because it does not have the necessary information or methods to implement. The price of these basic products is determined by the market of the big companies that buy them and the countries that manufacture them can say very little about it. This makes them financially dependent on agents who in turn are the ones who usually invest in the product (Cooke 2004).

Increase in foreign loans

One of the defining characteristics of these countries is usually their foreign debt, which is considered a vicious circle from which very few people can escape. By relying on both countries or foreign companies to negotiate or exchange their products and resources, they lose almost all of their contracts. They need to borrow to acquire the required technology and knowledge required for their production activities. Still, after implementing them, they do not receive much to cover the investment received for their products. As a result, its debt increases every day, and its GDP is proportionately lower (David 1991).

Significant population growth

In general, these countries have provocative population growth, resulting in very high infant mortality rates. To overcome this issue, policies have been developed that seek to curb the birth rate, ranging from the distribution of free contraceptives to restrictions on those who have legal rights. But there are more children than allowed (Cooke 2004).

The reason for stopping the increase in birth rates in these countries is that where there is a large population, very few resources should already be distributed to as many people as possible, so that there is less equality for everyone. When more people are available than resources, it's about population, which is a common feature of the Third World (David 1991).

Political instability

Historically, and until recently, Third World countries were colonies of other countries. Borders and political differences arose between the nations that colonized them, conflicts which still exist today. In such countries, dictatorship is common, and democracy is lacking, so rebellion, corruption, armed conflict, violence and insurgency or civil war are very common for reasons ranging from religious to economic. This exacerbates the plight of these countries and hinders their economic recovery (Harris 1987).

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Lack of health and education system

Due to low economic status and high congestion, it is difficult for all residents to get a better health and education system. As a result, many of these countries have diseases that are virtually non-existent, illiteracy rates are high and access to education is low. Outbreaks appear to be exacerbated in Third World countries, due to a lack of medical supplies (such as vaccines and antibiotics, among others) and a lack of systems that provide some supply to the entire country (Cooke 2004).

Standards of living

In addition to political, technical, economic, health and education issues, the quality of life of people living in Third World countries is severely affected by the absence of labor rights. As a result of globalization, large international companies moved part of their production process to these countries because of how cheap the labor force (mostly unskilled) could be, including child labor and labor exploitation which often considered slavery and Poverty rate. Another important feature of Third World countries is that they have high levels of poverty, the causes of which are considered both external and internal (Harris 1987).

Various international and non-governmental organizations are trying to implement measures to reduce these levels, but inequality in these countries is still uncommon.

A small part of the population concentrates on almost all economic and political power, it forms the considered elite or upper class, while the rest live a life of uncertainty called poverty or extreme poverty (i.e., lower social class). That is why the absence of a middle class is common. Gross Domestic Product (GDP) or per capita income of these countries is generally the lowest in the world and often declines (Escobar 2011).

Term replacement

The term "third world" or "third world countries" has been replaced by developing, under developing or backward countries, which, more or less, meet the above characteristics due to the inevitability of a natural disaster., But for historical reasons (social, political or economic) (Cooke 2004).

Human Development Index (HDI)

With the Human Development Index (HDI) measurement, the United Nations (UN) ranks as the developed countries with the lowest indicators. This measurement considers life expectancy at birth, adult literacy rate, enrollment rate at all three levels of education, and each country's GDP. The United Nations has designated the following developed countries:

This feature includes loss or lack of access to essential resources such as drinking water, food, electricity, and information, either due to lack of proper distribution system or due to pollution or climate change, which has affected them. All of this increases the mortality rate every day and lowers the life expectancy of its population (Worsley, 1970).

Poverty Rate

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The UN and the Third World Countries

The United Nations, formed after the League of Nations on June 26, 1945, has become controversial. It has deviated from its original purpose and started following the lead of a few

preferred powers. The League of Nations played an active role in the economic, economic, and political arenas but failed to bring peace to the world. In order to save the world from the Third World War, all the member states of the United Nations are members of the General Assembly, while the number of members of the Security Council is (11) with five permanent members who have veto power. These countries are the United States, Britain, Russia, France, and China. The General Assembly meets once a year but may be convened at any time in an emergency (Tomlinson, 2003).

Let us now turn to the question of whether the United Nations has played its role well in recent years. Has the world really moved away from the dangers of war? Do member states still have full confidence in their performance?

In the last two decades, the world has been divided into two parts. The factionalism of the United States and Russia has crushed Asian and Third World countries. After the disintegration of Russia in 1991, the world changed into a new world order. The G8, an organization of economically and economically stable countries, emerged, while staggering and crutching countries resorted to the SARC. Rich countries became richer and poorer countries went below the poverty line. As a result, the current division of the world is a division between the rich and the poor. According to experts, the third world war will now be between the rich and the poor. For developing countries, the United Nations is no longer a forum for resolving issues but a means of using force against them (Harris 1987).

Decisions made by the United Nations in the last few years have been made only to please the superpowers. They had the power of powerful factions. Whether it's the use of force in Iraq, the military operation in Afghanistan, the sanctions on Iran's nuclear program, or the resolutions against North Korea, these are all unilateral and counter-terrorism tactics. After 9/11, the United Nations emerged as the only diplomatic institution of the United States and Britain. Unjustified military action in Iraq has undermined world peace. The whole world is on fire right now. Suicide bombings and daily attacks on US and British troops have become a source of concern for the United States and its allies. It was not long before the United Nations authorized an invasion of Afghanistan. Under the pretext of capturing Osama and Mullah Omar, the scope of this war has been extended to the borders of Pakistan. The operation in the Northern Areas and Swat is being carried out at the behest of the forces behind it. Today, nations are concerned about Iran's nuclear program. Today, North Korea's nuclear program is a wake-up call (Tomlinson 2003).

Who will guarantee the nuclear program of the United States, Britain, France and China?

Why doesn't the United Nations see terrorism in Palestine and Kashmir, which is growing on the bones of the United States and Britain? Why is the scale of quality different here? Why does the US veto the pet against Israel? Why is no action taken against Dina's biggest terrorist country India which is crushing 700,000 innocent Kashmiris? Humans do not live here. Is the violation of human rights hidden from the eyes of the United Nations?

It is better to stop this drama now which has no authority to implement its own resolutions. The silence of the world on the aggression of Israel and India is significant. Perhaps Third World countries are doomed. It is futile to associate them with any hope from the American people.

A living example of Third world practices

A living example of Third World practices is the recent ban on some of Pakistan's religious parties by the Security Council. Three religious parties, were banned without hearing Pakistan's position after the Bombay bombings. It is tantamount to robbing any country of its sovereignty. Action against any country without investigation, without evidence and without solid evidence is open terrorism and bullying (Roul 2015).

United Nations a Tool for Some Powerful Countries

Today, third countries or developing countries are fighting for their survival. They face internal and external threats. Unfortunately, there is no world forum to hear them. The United Nations has become a tool of some powerful countries. Some countries are using it against weak and economically weak countries to achieve their goals. The currency of these countries is depreciating against the dollar day by day. Inflation is on the rise. 33% of the budget of a developing country like Pakistan is being spent on the markup of these loans. Programs of organizations like UNESCO and UNICEF are like charities for these countries. In these circumstances, instead of healing the wounds of these countries, the United Nations is working to increase the conditions every year. The global market, which is monopolized by a few countries and is favored by the United Nations, is bent on destroying the economic condition of third world countries. In these circumstances, instead of healing the wounds of these countries, the United Nations is working to increase the conditions every year (Tomlinson, 2003).

Third World Countries in the World

In today's world UN has set few parameters for the third world indication. The names of the countries are mentioned as under:

- Africa

In Africa, Angola, Burkina Faso, Benin, Burundi, Comoros, Chad, Ethiopia, Eritrea, Guyana, Gambia, Guyana – Basao, Liberia, Lesotho, Madagascar, Financial, Malawi, Mauritania, Nigeria, Mozambique, United Republic of Tanzania, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Sao Tome and Principe, Rwanda, Central African Democracy, Senegal, Somalia, Sierra Leone, Sudan, South Sudan, Uganda, Zambia, Djibouti, Gabon, and Algeria are listed as underdeveloped countries by UN indicators (UNDP 2021).

- United States

In US, Haiti, Belize, Costa Rica, Colombia, Cuba, Saviour, Ecuador, Nicaragua, Venezuela, Paraguay, Panama, Peru, Uruguay, and Dominican Republic are listed as underdeveloped countries by UN indicators (UNDP 2021).

- Asia and Oceania

In Asia and Oceania, Bangladesh, Afghanistan, Bhutan, Burma, Caribbean, Cambodia, Yemen, Solomon Islands, Lao People's Democratic Republic, Nepal, East Timor, Vanuatu, Mongolia, Saudi Arabia, Syria, and Iraq are listed as underdeveloped countries by UN indicators (UNDP 2021).

Conclusion

The global market, which is monopolized by a few countries and is favored by the United Nations, is bent on destroying the economic condition of third world countries. The point is to revisit the United Nations charters, which do have the power to make independent decisions and their implications. Third world countries are no longer afraid of war, they don't want atomic bombs. They need a livelihood, not a weapon to fight, or the veto power must end. Or all stakeholders should also have the power of veto power to represent their countries. Then the balance of power will change and the exploitation of third world countries will stop.

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